

Carbonised Palm Kernel Shell Effect on the Physico-Chemical Properties of Clay-Sand Mixture

O. A. Abiola, A. O. Oke

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife.

ABSTRACT

Carbonised palm kernel shell was employed to improve water purification property of clay-sand mixture used as water filter in the rural areas. Quantity of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay-sand mixture was varied. Different proportions of carbonised palm kernel shell were mixed with certain proportion of clay-sand mixture and used as samples-mix for the different analysis. Each samples-mix was tested for various physical as well as chemical properties. The results showed that linear shrinkage ranges between 0% and 6%, bulk density ranges between 1.02 g/cm³ to 2.21 g/cm³, modulus of rupture of 46.54 kg/cm³, reduction in water absorption of 25.21 to 12.31% and weight of the various samples-mix decrease with carbon addition while permeability to air, apparent porosity and flow rate rise. Samples with 0%, 5%, 10% and 15% carbon were stable at the calcinations temperature of 1450⁰C. The chemical analysis of the pure clay sample revealed 55.91% of SiO₂. It can thus be concluded that the carbonized palm kernel shell in the mixture of the clay-sand is inversely proportional to the linear shrinkage, bulk density, modulus of rupture, water absorption and weight of the sample but directly proportional to permeability, apparent porosity and flow rate.

Keywords: Clay-sand mixture, Carbonised palm kernel shell, Physico-chemical properties, chemical properties

1 Introduction

Design principles in recent years have relied on the physical and chemical properties of materials (Bandosz, 1992). Performance of materials depend largely on its physical properties which when wrongly selected can result into hazard, equipment failure and/or loss of capital.

Clay is hydrous aluminum phyllosilicates, sometimes with variable amounts of iron, magnesium, alkali metals, alkaline earths and other cations. Clays have structures similar to the micas and therefore form flat hexagonal sheets. Clay minerals are common weathering products and low temperature hydrothermal alteration products (Ehlmann *et al.*, 2013). Kaolin, ball, slip, earthenware, bentonite, stoneware and fireclay are the different types of clay sand and are generally classified as either residual or sedimentary (Adelabu, 2012; Adindu *et al.*, 2014). Clay minerals are very common in fine grained sedimentary rocks such as shale, mudstone and siltstone and in fine

grained metamorphic slate and phyllite (Nandi, 2017).

Pure clay has many uses, when moulded and fired practically have no porosity that can allow air passage (Droste, 2002) and unless sharp sand aggregate is added, it will filter little or no water (Oke and Omoleye, 2006). After recognising the limitations of clay in the purification of water, Rytwo *et al.* (2006) stated that though clay add more micro-organism to water filtrates, it is helpful in the removal of hazardous chemicals due to its impressive adsorption properties. Natural clay minerals adsorb cations and non-charged hydrophilic compounds almost do not interact with anions and hydrophobic pollutants as most organic pollutants, including naphthalene and phenolic derivatives. By pre-treating clay and adding carbon to it, its properties are no doubt an influence to removing large amounts of pollutants from water (Oke and Abiola, 2013).

Meanwhile, Palm kernel shell, an agricultural by product (waste) of palm tree is found to be abundant in Nigeria, as a waste, its disposal is a serious environmental issue (Owolarafe and Oni, 2011). The carbonised state of the palm kernel shell has been employed by many researchers in the purification of water (Inegbenebor, *et al.*, 2012; Oke and Abiola, 2013; Okoroigwe, 2014). Oke and Abiola (2013) investigated the use of clay-sand mixture mixed with

□e-mail: abiolaolurantiadetunji@yahoo.com
Second Author, okekola@oauife.edu.ng. Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife

various percentage of carbonised Palm kernel shell (filter) to remove physical or solid and chemical impurity from water and found it to be effective and of good value. Though, soil scientists have in the past placed most emphasis on chemical properties of soils, increasing interest is now being shown in physical properties as well.

The work of Oke and Omoleye (2006) showed that at a certain percentage of sand the mixture of clay and sand, the rigidity and other physical properties was greatly affected. Consequently, the work seeks to investigate the physical properties of these filters so as to be able to predict the optimum quantity.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Raw material

The major material used in the course of this work was clay, obtained from Ipetumodu, Ife North Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria; alongside sand which was also readily available. The other major important material was the activated carbon made from palm kernel shell. Clay-sand mixture with 90% clay and 10% sand of particle size of between 0.5mm to 1mm was used for the experiments, this specification was adopted in the cause of this work because according to Oke and Omoleye (2006), it will best serve filtration purposes while Oke and Abiola (2013) established its potential in removing both physical and chemical water contaminants; while carbon was varied from 5% up to 50% as it was added to clay/sand mixture. This limit is maintained because the sample with excess of 50% carbonised palm kernel shell could not withstand an erect posture because the mixture is not well bonded together.

2.2 Materials preparation

The clay obtained in the raw form and the carbonised palm kernel shell was crushed separately to smaller particle by the use of hammer. The as-mined sand was washed and dried naturally to remove impurities. The dry ground clay was passed through a specified sieve size in order to allow finer particles of the clay pass through the mesh leaving the coarser particles. The particles of the sand and carbonised palm kernel shell were also sieved separately to obtain homogenous mixture of clay and sand with carbonised palm kernel shell. A well sieve clay and sand were first measured and mixed in the ratio 45% to 5% respectively by volume.

Ten Sample-mix were labeled A-J and prepared with sample A contained 5% carbon, sample B contained 10%

carbon and carbon content was increased arithmetically, thus with common difference of 5% up to 50% carbon content for sample J. The control experiment was performed on sample-mix marked 'X' which is purely clay/sand mixture (i.e has no carbon addition). Each selected sample-mix of clay/sand mixture and carbonised palm kernel shell was mixed and blended together by piling the clay/sand mixture and the carbonised palm kernel shell into a cone-shaped dune. Physical and chemical properties of each sample-mix were then evaluated.

2.3 Physical properties

Physical properties are properties that are measurable, whose value can be used to describe the state of a physical system. Physical properties such as: permeability, linear shrinkage, bulk density, refractoriness, modulus of rupture, water absorption flow rate and weight of the various sample-mixes were evaluated using their respective procedures:

2.3.1 Refractoriness

The refractoriness of the various sample-mixes was determined using the method of Pyrometric Cone Equivalence (PCE) in accordance with the standard test method for pyrometric cone equivalent of refractory materials used by Mark (2010). The refractoriness for each test cone is the number of standard pyrometric cone that has bent over to a similar extent as the test cone. The temperature corresponding to the cone number was read off from the ASTM Orton Series.

2.3.2 Permeability

Test samples were prepared from each sample-mix to a specification of 5.08cm height from a standard rammer. The test pieces were air-dried for 24 hours to reduce the water level for a safe oven drying. The samples are then transferred to the oven for proper drying at 110°C for 12 hours. The samples were completely sealed on the sides, and the lower surfaces were exposed to an orifice. A cylinder was filled with 2000cm³ of water and the bell jar was put in place. The orifice was then opened and the times taken for 2000cm³ of water to displace equal volume of air through the specimens were taken. The pressure differences between the surfaces were measured using a manometer. Permeability was then calculated from equation (1) in line with Grimshaw (1971).

$$P_A = \frac{VH}{APt} \quad (1)$$

where, P_A is value of permeability; V is volume of air (cm^3), H is height of specimen (cm), A is cross sectional area of specimen (cm^2), P is pressure of air in cm^3 of water and t is time (minutes).

2.3.3 Linear shrinkage

Linear shrinkage, the reduction in size of a clay samples when it is fired in a kiln was evaluated following the method used by Mark (2010). Test pieces were made into standard slabs using the various sample-mixes. The test pieces were marked along a line in order to maintain the same position after heat treatment. The samples were air-dried for 24 hours and oven dried at 110°C for another 24 hours. They were then fired at 1100°C for 6 hours. The test pieces were cooled to room temperature and distance between the two ends of the slab were measured using Vernier caliper after oven and fire drying of the samples. The linear shrinkage for each sample was then calculated from equation (2).

$$S_L = 100\%(D_L - F_L) / D_L \quad (2)$$

where, S_L is linear shrinkage (g/cm^3), D_L is dried length (mm) and F_L is fired length (mm)

2.3.4 Bulk density

Bulk density is the weight per unit volume of the refractory including the volume of open pore space. This was obtained by weighing the samples (60mm x 60mm x 15mm bricks produced from the sample-mixes) in air and suspended water, using an electronic analytical balance model HM300 to an accuracy of 0.001g to obtain the bulk density as presented by Hassan et al. (2014) in equation (3). The true dry weight was obtained by first air-drying the sample for 24 hours, oven dry at 1100°C , and then cooled in the desiccator.

$$\rho_B = \frac{D}{(W - S)} \rho_w \quad (3)$$

where, ρ_B is bulk density (g/cm^3), D is weight dry sample (g), W weight of soaked sample suspended in air (g), S is weight dry sample suspended in cold water (g), and ρ_w is density of water.

2.3.5 Apparent porosity

Apparent porosity, the ratio of space taken up by the pores in a material to its total volume was investigated following the method used by Mark (2010). Pieces of test bricks prepared from the various sample-mix were air-dried for 24

hours and then oven-dried at 110°C for 24 hours. After, the pieces were fired to temperature of 1100°C , cooled and then transferred into desiccators, it was then weighed using an electronic analytical balance model HM300 to nearest 0.001g. The specimens were transferred into a 250ml beaker in empty vacuum desiccators. Water was introduced into the beaker until the test pieces were completely immersed. The specimen was allowed to soak in boiled water for 30 minutes being agitated from time to time to assist to release trapped air bubbles. The specimens were transferred into vacuum desiccators to cool. The specimens were weighed suspended in water using beaker placed on balance as well as soaked weight determined to the nearest 0.001g and apparent porosity was calculated from equation (4).

$$P_a = \frac{W - D}{W - S} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

where P_a is apparent porosity, W is soaked weight, S is suspended weight and D is dried weight.

2.3.6 Modulus of rupture

Representative test bricks made from the various sample-mixes was prepared and air-dried for 24 hours. The pieces were then oven-dried at 110°C for another 24 hours. The pieces were fired to a temperature of 1100°C , the length and diameter were determined and then place in a tensometer where load was applied on the pieces of test bricks until it breaks. The applied load just before the different samples broke was taking from the tensometer and recorded. Modulus of rupture was calculated from equation (5) in line with Aramide (2012).

$$MoR = \frac{3PL}{2D^3} \quad (5)$$

where MoR is modulus of rupture (Kg/cm^2), P is total load at which the specimen failed (Kg), L is distance between support, that is bearing edge (cm) and D is diameter of the specimen (cm).

2.3.7 Water absorption

In this test, the samples prepared from the various sample-mixes were placed inside porcelain crucible and then dried in an oven at a temperature of 105°C for 24 hours to obtain the dry weight. The samples were weighed using an electronic analytical balance model HM300 that can be readable up to 0.001g. The adsorption of material (total water adsorption) is define as the increase in the weight of the material due to moisture in the air, and can be calculated

using equation (6) in line with the work of Johari (2011).

$$A_w \% = \frac{W_b - D_a}{W_a - W_c} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

where A_w is water absorption or moisture content of specimen (%), W_a is weight of specimen after oven dried for 24 hours (g), W_b is weight of specimen after 24 hours in desiccators (g), and W_c is weight of crucible (g).

2.3.8 Flow rate

Flow rate, the time taking for a particular volume of liquid to pass through a channel was evaluated with the various mix. For accurate measurement, a 10ml pipette was used to pipette the water sample into filter mould sample twice to make 20ml of water sample. A stop watch was set in place to determine the time taken for the 20ml of water to pass each various samples of clay-sand mixture and carbonised palm kernel shell. Flow rate was calculated on the bases of 1litre (1000ml) using equation (7) below.

$$F = V/T \quad (7)$$

where F is flow rate (Ls^{-1}), V is volume of water (L), T is time taken for the volume water to pass through the sample.

2.3.9 Weight

The weight of each sample was determined to the nearest 0.01g using a weighing balance.

2.4 Chemical analysis of clay materials

The chemical analysis of the sample (pure clay) was carried out using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) method to identify its chemical composition. 0.5g clay sample was weighed, ground to 150 μ m mesh, and was then transferred into the crucible. Also, 1.4g of flux (1.2g of Na_2CO_3 + 0.2g of boric acid); was added, mixed well and cover. The mixture was heated at 1200 $^{\circ}C$ for 5 minutes. This was removed and the base of the crucible was quenched in distilled water. The crucible was then placed in a 250ml beaker, and a 60ml of HCL was added to it. The solution was then left in a warmer, agitating at interval, until the dissolution was completed. The solution was diluted to the appropriate volume. Table 1 shows the conditions that must be met in other to arrive at the best result for the test as close as possible to the result chemical analysis presented in this paper.

During the combustion process, we obtained acetylene- NO_2 flow mixture for elements Al, Si and Ti, and acetylene-air flow mixture for Ca, Fe, Na, K and Mg; which helps to increasing aggregate stability, permeability,

friability, porosity, and hydraulic conductivity, and reducing swelling, clay dispersion, bulk density, and modulus of rupture of the clay samples (Zhang et al., 2017). The combustion process was ionised from the low energy level to high energy level to enhance and facilitate the combustion process.

Table 1 Instrumental conditions for chemical analysis of clay

Element	Air flow (min^{-1})	Acetylene flow (min^{-1})	Wave length (nm)	Lamp current (mA)
Al	4.5 – 5.5 NO_2	4.2 – 5.0	309.3	8 – 10
Si	4.5 – 5.5 NO_2	4.2 – 5.0	251.6	12 – 15
Ca	4.5 – 5.5	1.1 – 1.3	422.7	8 – 10
Fe	4.5 – 5.5	1.1 – 1.3	248.3	4 – 5
Ti	4.5 – 5.5 NO_2	4.2 – 5.0	364.3	12 – 15
Na	4.5 – 5.5	0.9 – 1.1	589.0	7 – 8
K	4.5 – 5.5	0.9 – 1.1	765.5	7 – 8
Mg	4.5 – 5.5	0.9 – 1.1	285.2	4

3 Results and Discussions

The results of the physical properties of the clay-sand mixture, mixed with variable quantities of carbonised palm kernel shell are presented below as well as the chemical analysis.

3.1 Physical properties

3.1.1 Refractoriness

Samples containing 0 to 15% carbon show no noticeable failure up to a temperature of 1450 $^{\circ}C$ as shown in Table 2. Samples with 20% carbon up to 50% carbon failed at temperature of 1450 $^{\circ}C$. This value showed that the sintering temperatures of the clay are high with reduced carbon percentage which is an indication of good refractoriness. The clay fails within the range of 1589 - 1720 $^{\circ}C$ for fireclays according to Grimshaw (1971).

3.1.2 Permeability

The permeability of all the samples are within the range of 84 – 167 as shown in Figure 1. Increase carbonised palm kernel shell results in increase permeability. Permeability is a function of the system of the two or more fluids and the porous material (Abaci et al., 1997). The refractory under the influence of gases and liquid should be impervious; this would help to eliminate leakage of gases and penetration of liquids through the walls of the furnace (Chester, 1973).

Table 2 Refractoriness of clay-sand mixture and carbonised

palm kernel shell.

% of carbonised palm kernel shell	Sample notation	Refractoriness (°C)
0%	X	1450
5%	A	1450
10%	B	1450
15%	C	1450
20%	D	<1450
25%	E	<1450
30%	F	<1450
35%	G	<1450
40%	H	<1450
45%	I	<1450
50%	J	<1450

3.1.2 Permeability

The permeability of all the samples are within the range of 84 – 167 as shown in Figure 1. Increase carbonised palm kernel shell results in increase permeability. Permeability is a function of the system of the two or more fluids and the porous material (Abaci et al., 1997). The refractory under the influence of gases and liquid should be impervious; this would help to eliminate leakage of gases and penetration of liquids through the walls of the furnace (Chester, 1973).

Figure 1. Permeability against the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture

3.1.3 Linear shrinkage

The average linear shrinkage for all the samples is within the range of 0 – 6% as shown in Figure 2. It is similar to the work of Titiladunayo and Fapetu (2011) which stated that linear shrinkage of pure clay from the following areas are as indicated: Ikere Ekiti clay - 5%, Fagbohun Ekiti clay - 2%, Ishan Ekiti clay - 1.5% and Ara Ekiti clay - 1.9%. The results show that carbonised Palm kernel shell has no serious effect on the linear shrinkage. Higher shrinkage may result in warping and cracking of the brick and this may cause loss of heat in the furnace.

It could be observed that there is no appreciable change

in the values of linear shrinkage of the samples and even less, when compared to the 7 – 10% linear shrinkage values recommended by Chester (1973).

Figure 2. Linear shrinkage (%) against the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture

3.1.4 Bulk density

The average bulk density of the clay samples was within the range of 1.07 – 2.21 g/cm³ as shown in Figure 3. The bulk density for 0% carbonised palm kernel shell (Pure Ipetumodu clay) is similar to the bulk density of pure Fagbohun Ekiti clay (2.0%), Ishan Ekiti clay (2.0%) and Ara Ekiti clay (1.9%) as reported by Titiladunayo and Fapetu (2011). It is believed that increase bulk density will increase volume stability, heat capacity, as well as the resistance to abrasion and slag penetration which in turn will improve the furnace lining (Bhatia, 2012). The reduced values of bulk density as carbon is increased, simply shows that addition of carbon will hamper the quality of the clay to be use as furnace lining.

Figure 3. Bulk density (g/cm³) against the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture

3.1.5 Apparent porosity

The values for the apparent porosity of the samples are within the 26.32 – 42.75% as shown in Figure 4. The apparent porosity for 0% carbonised palm kernel shell (Pure Ipetumodu clay) which is 26.32%, falls within the range 19.10 and 31.44% as reported by Titiladunayo and Fapetu (2011). According to Bhatia (2012) refractory materials with high porosity, a measure of effective open

pore space cannot withstand high temperature molten slag and direct flame impingement as they are likely to shrink when subjected to such conditions. The result shows that increasing the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell will affect its refractoriness but improves its filtration properties.

Figure 4. Apparent porosity (%) against the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture

3.1.6 Modulus of rupture

The results of modulus of rupture for pure clay-sand mixture, without carbon was 46.54 Kg/cm³ as shown in Figure 5. The samples' modulus of rupture started to reduce steadily with the introduction of carbon and as carbon addition reached 35%, modulus of rupture reduced to zero. The modulus of rupture is an indication of strength (Alege and Alege, 2013), the result shows that carbon addition hampers the strength of clay-sand mixture.

Figure 5. Modulus of rupture (Kg/cm³) against the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture

3.1.7 Water absorption

The results show that water absorption reduces from 25.21% to 12.31% as addition of carbonised palm kernel shell increases (Figure 6). This could be due to the non-plastic nature of carbon. So, increasing the carbon content in the sample-mix will reduce the water that the sample can absorb.

Figure 6. Water absorption (%) against the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture

3.1.8 Flow rate

The results show that clay-sand mixture with no carbon addition has little or no pores to allow water passage. Carbon addition create pores with clay-sand mixture allowing a minimum flow rate of 0.000159 litre/min (for 5% carbon) while the maximum flow rate was 0.013043 (for 50% carbon) as shown in Figure 7. The flow rate for the samples containing 30% and 35% carbon addition seems irregular and may be due to experimental error.

Figure 7. Water flow rate (Litre/min) against the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture

3.1.9 Weight

The results show that the weight (hence the density) of the samples reduces with increased carbon. The maximum weight is 860g (for 0% carbon) while the minimum weight is 385g (for 50% carbon) as shown in Figure 8. (The volume is constant for all the samples)

Figure . 8. Weight (g) against the percentage of carbonised palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture

3.2 Chemical properties

The result of the chemical composition of the pure Ipetumodu clay sample used for this experiment reveals that the clay has higher percentage composition of SiO_2 (55.91%) compare to other compounds as shown in Table 3. This is the same as the result when compare to Oke and Omidiji (2016) who use a different approach. The result is also similar to the report of Titiladunayo and Fapetu (2011) which revealed that clays are anhydrous complex compound of Aluminum (Al_2O_3) and silica (SiO_2), that exist in various proportion and contain varied amount of impurities of iron, organic matters and residual minerals. The significance of these chemical properties is to determine the degree of purity of the clay because content like Fe_2O_3 is an impurity (Ayhan, *et al.*, 2011).

Table 3 Chemical composition of clay samples

Chemical composition	% composition
SiO_2	55.91
Al_2O_3	29.91
Fe_2O_3	1.91
CaO	0.2
MgO	0.4
K_2O	1.9
Na_2O	0.2
TiO_2	0.9

4 Conclusions.

The result showed that the quantity of the carbonized palm kernel shell in the mixture of the clay-sand is inversely proportional to the linear shrinkage, bulk density, modulus of rupture, water absorption and weight of the sample but directly proportional to permeability, apparent porosity and flow rate. The refractoriness of the sample with no/low carbon content (0%, 5%, 10%, 15% carbon) remain stable at 21450°C. This showed that the carbonized palm kernel shell as no effect on the refractoriness.

References

- Abaci, S.; Edwards, J.S. and B.N. Whittaker (1997). Relative Performance Measurements for Two Phase Flow in Unconsolidated Sands. *Mine Water and the Environmental*, 11(2): 11-26.
- Adelabu, O.S. (2012): Documentation, application and utilization of clay minerals in Kaduna State (Nigeria). licensee InTech. http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0_pp3-20. Access September 18, 2016.
- Adindu, C.I., Moses, J., Thaddeus, C.A. and Tse, D.T. (2014): Exploring ceramic raw materials in Nigeria and their contribution to nation's development. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 3(9): 127-134.
- Alege, E.K and T.S. Alege (2013). Selected Clays of the Bida and Anambra Basins of Nigeria: Their Characteristics, Fired Properties and Ceramic-Suitability. *International Journal of Science and Technology*. 2(7): 560 – 567.
- Aramide, F.O. (2012). Effect of Firing Temperature on Mechanical Properties of Fired Masonry Bricks Produced from Ipetumodu clay. *Leonardo Journal of Sciences*. 21: 70 – 82.
- Ayhan, F.D.; Temel, H.A. and V. Bozkurt (2011). Removal of Impurities from Tailing (Quartz) Obtained from Bitlis Kyanite Ore by Flotation Method, *International Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 1(1): 74-81.
- Bandosz, T.J; Jagiello, J; Amankwah, K.A.G and J.A. Schwarz (1992). Chemical and Structural Properties of Clay Minerals Modified by Inorganic and Organic Material. *Clay Minerals*. 27: 435-444.
- Bhatia, A. (2012). Overview of Refractory Materials. PDH online Course M158 (3PDH), pp 2 - 54. Available online at www.pdhonline.com/courses/m158/m158content.pdf
- Chester, J.H. (1973). *Refractories, Production and Properties*. The Iron and Steel Institution, London.
- Droste. R.L. (2002). *The Theory and Practice of Water and Wastewater Treatment*. Hamilton Printing Company, Castleton, NY 12033.
- Ehlmann, B.L.; Berger, G.; Mangold N.; Michalski, J.R.; Catling, D.C.; Ruff, S.W.; Chassefière, E.; Niles, P.B.; Chevrier, V. and Poulet, F. (2013). Geochemical Consequences of Widespread Clay Mineral Formation in Mars' Ancient Crust. *Space Sci Rev*, 174: 329–364.
- Grimshaw. R.W. (1971). *The Chemistry and Physics of Clays*, 2nd Edition. Tata McGraw-Hill, New Delhi, India.

- Hassan, M.A; Yami, A.M; Raji, A and M.J. Ngala (2014). Effect of Sawdust and Rice Husk Additive on Properties of Local Refractory Clay. The International Journal of Engineering and Science. 3(8): 40 -44.
- Inegbenebor, A.I; Inegbenebor, A.O and H.I. Bayo (2012). Comparison of The Adsorptive Capacity of Raw Materials in Making Activated Carbon Filter for Purification of Water for Drinking. ARPN Journal of Science of Technology. 2(9): 754-760.
- Johari, I; Said, S; Jaya, R.P; Bakar, B.H.A and Z.A. Ahmad (2011). Chemical and Physical Properties of Pired-Clay Brick at Different Type of Rice Husk Ash. International Conference on Environment Science and Engineering IPCBEE. 8: 171-174.
- Mark, U. (2010). Characterization of Iberé and Oboro Clay Deposits in Abia State, Nigeria for Refractory Applications. International Journal of Natural and Applied Sciences. 6(3): 296-305.
- Nandi, A. (2017). Classification of Rocks. Encyclopedia of Earth Science Series, Springer International Publishing, pp. 1-4
- Oke, A.O and O.A. Abiola (2013). Investigation into the Use of Clay and Carbonised Palm Kernel Shell Mixture as Water Filter. Journal of Engineering Research (JER), University of Lagos. 18(1): 87-96.
- Oke, A.O and B.V. Omidiji (2016). Investigation of Same Moulding Properties of a Nigeria Clay-Bonded Sand. Archives of Foundry Engineering. 16(3): 71-76.
- Oke, A.O and J.A. Omoleye (2006). Investigation of Domestic Water Filters Made from Local Raw Material. Nigerian Journal of Mechanical Engineering. 4(1): 28 – 40.
- Okoroigwe, E.C; Saffron, C.M and P.D. Kamdem (2014). Charaterization of Palm Kernel Shell for Materials Reinforcement and Water Treatment. Journal of Chemical Engineering and Materials Science. 5(1): 1-6.
- Owolarafe, O.K and O.A Oni (2011). Modern Mill Technology and Centralized Processing System, An Alternative for Moving Performance of Palm Oil Mills in Abia state. Nigeria Technology in Society. 33: 12–22.
- Rytwo G; Kohavi Y.; Botnick I and Y. Gonen (2006). Nanosized Carbon Material-Activated Carbon Composite. Tel Hai Academic College, Environmental Sciences Department, Upper Galilee 12210, Israel. Available online at <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/journal/0169-1317>.
- Titiladunayo, I.F and O.P. Fapetu (2011). Selection of Appropriate Clay for Furnace Lining in a Pyrolysis Process. Journal of Emerging Trends in Engineering and Applied Science. 4(3): 938 – 945.
- Zhang, T; Hu, S and W. Yang (2017). Variations of Escherichia Coli O157:H7 Survival in Purple Soils. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 14: 1-9

Journal Address:
Business Manager
Journal of Applied Science, Engineering and Technology
(JASET),
Faculty of Technology,
University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
Email: jasetui3@gmail.com

Visit us on www.jaset.ui.edu.ng